

Brand Consciousness: Implications for The Upcoming and Existing Branded Companies

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Abstract

This research aims to explore the impact of various factors on brand consciousness, focusing on consumer behavior in Lahore. The study will formulate hypotheses to delineate the connections between different factors and brand consciousness. The investigation will delve into the underlying reasons for brand consciousness, considering established factors such as price, quality, and brand awareness. The key determinants under scrutiny include affordability (price), product quality, and the level of brand awareness. A quantitative research methodology will be employed for gathering data. Subsequently, the collected data will be analyzed using SPSS, aligning with the quantitative nature of the study. Additionally, the research will address the significance of the findings, as well as the study's validity, reliability, and its scope and limitations.

Keywords: Quality, Affordability, Variety, Brand awareness.

Introduction

Branding is a major topic of study in market discipline, began in earnest in 1970's. Books and articles have tackled the topic of branding from different perceptions. Specially, a good portion of the research on brands like brand loyalty, brand switching, and brand extensions.

Shopping is loved by a large number of people throughout the world. Enter a mall and look around. You'll find many options; be it clothing, cosmetics, shoes, perfumes, fashion accessories and others. You will find daily use items and fashion related things around you. Yet, you go around in search of your signature brands and brush aside others. Some of you might have a taste for any particular brand, and deem it to be something you cannot compromise for other extraneous products from varying other manufacturers. Have you ever thought why? Ever wondered about the question of being brand-conscious animal? Does brand consciousness play a major role in making a person's personality different from the one who love dipping things in branded sauces?

The answer of all above questions is brand consciousness. Yes because people are conscious about what they are wearing that's why they choose branded product to be on a level in the society. They want to look more attractive and show the other people that they have wearied branded products. And people got attracted to them easily.

Brand consciousness extends beyond mere recognition or preference for brands. Individuals who are highly self-aware often place significant importance on the impression they create on others. Such individuals typically show a heightened concern for their physical appearance and adherence to fashion trends. They also desire to be recognized and distinguished based on their appearance and the fashion trends they adopt. Furthermore, these individuals tend to conform more closely to

societal standards and are more sensitive to the possibility of interpersonal rejection.

Brands have become ubiquitous in our lives, with corporations increasingly emphasizing the marketing of their brand names. Branded products have a unique ability to capture consumer attention, leading to an entirely new dimension in consumer behavior. In today's global market, being brand conscious is almost a necessity. A brand-conscious individual usually prefers purchasing products exclusively from well-known companies. These products must meet their specific demands and expectations to ensure satisfaction.

In market it is very necessary for companies to know people attract towards branded products and which attributes they prefer in it. After getting knowledge about people perceptions they can change or modify their strategies and attributes of products. When companies change their strategies and attributes they will easily able to capture the attraction of people towards their product. The person who is brand conscious he/she should know about all the brands in the market. And what are the new trends in the market.

As the world progressive day by day and large number of branded companies is existed in the market and also there is tough competition among competitors due to the entrance of new companies in the market. Every company wants to become the best in their field and satisfy their customer with their performance.

Its means youth is conscious but not very loyal to any brand either in cloths or shoes but the companies should not give them option to leave their brand they should give better performance to them and comfortable product then there is a chance that they will not shift to another brand.

The objective of this proposed study is to understand the role of brand name and to know the consciousness of people about the branded products and to ascertain about the market position of branded products, see whether people are buying them or not and what is the main reason to buy branded products.

Because there is not enough information about brand consciousness in the market so this study will help existing and upcoming companies in respect of launch new product and developed existing products according to demand of their customer. It will also help the companies to satisfy their customer and made their product better and attract more and more customers towards their brand. How Brand consciousness is affected by the number of factors and what are the outcomes drawn by the brand consciousness?

- The objective of this study is to check people are aware of brand qualities.
- Customers focus on brand name or features.
- Is brand consciousness is good for customers.

H1: People buy product based upon quality.

H2: People buy based upon a brand name more often than they buy based upon quality.

H3: People buy product based upon brand awareness.

The study significance is broad and helpful not only for branded companies also for the advertisement companies to advertise the products as people perceive. With the help of this study companies may know the perception of the people about branded products in accordance to launch new product in the market and make improvement in existing.

Literature Review

Shopping is a beloved pastime for many people around the globe. Step into any mall and you're met with a plethora of choices, from clothes and cosmetics to shoes, perfumes, and various fashion

accessories. Amidst these everyday and fashionable items, many shoppers seek out their preferred brands, often overlooking alternatives. For some, loyalty to a specific brand is non-negotiable, overshadowing products from other manufacturers. Brands have become a pervasive presence, with corporations investing heavily in brand marketing. As a result, branded products often draw more consumer attention, carving out a unique niche in the marketplace.

Brand consciousness refers to the recognition and differentiation of a brand as a unique entity. It revolves around the image and perception of the brand. The reason behind people's brand consciousness is significant. Brands have a powerful influence on consumer mindset, shaping thoughts and preferences. Over time, this influence can transform a brand into a consumer habit and eventually a perceived necessity.

As we know that most of the people are brand consciousness and the people of our country are going towards fashion and they are more aware of latest fashion, trend and style. Marx (1995) Explained in his work that mostly people are brand conscious and very loyal. From the last few years people are moving towards latest fashion and trends, not even youngster but working people are also moving towards branded products and woman either house wives or working women are also like to look fashionable. That's why they have become more brands conscious and loyal.

Anshul khandelwal (2012) found out that "different age groups of the people have different preferences regarding the brands". Everybody have their own choice of brand because different age groups have different perception about brand. Some group of people prefers one brand in clothes then the other group of people will prefer the same thing that is not possible. Because everybody have their own choices either in clothes, shoes or perfumes etc. As we can see that mostly youngster boys like to wear casual dresses but if we see a man who is working in an office he will like to wear formal dresses for office use.

According to Lie beck (1996) "Younger age levels have become desirable targets because of their purchasing power". Girls and boys now a day's want to purchase things quickly that they see and like more because they want to look more attractive and stylish in front of their friend and relatives. And companies also target them and make their product more good and stylish to attract the young girls and boys. When girls and boys attracted towards one branded product that they like, they will love to buy it. They will definitely not switch to another branded product if they are conscious about it and are loyal with it.

With the advancement in technology market trends also changed and number of branded companies established in the market and facing different type of challenges. As we know that in market there are different companies to serve their product for their customers. When there is an entry of a new brand in the market so the war will start in between different brands to satisfy their customer. And this war will tend them to change their strategies to attract their customer. And these new strategies and advancement in technology will help them to stay in the market and compete with their competitors.

We know that youth now likes more new styles and trends they are more brand aware and conscious not only here in Pakistan but also globally youth is liking branded products. Brand consciousness is not in the western countries it has also become more important for the students of Pakistan because the people of Pakistan are now more conscious about their style and looks. This shows the increasing level of consciousness among the youngsters. They probably made an ideal in their mind that may be an actor, singer, or a leader people follow or copy their styles and want to become like them. And some make their own styles.

Mostly people attract through advertisements of product if the advertisement part is strong then people become attracted towards that product and wish to have that product in their hands. Advertisement plays a significant role in today's competitive market. Today, many new institutes and business emerging within advertisement like event management, internet marketing and even branded companies also promote their product in market through advertisement. Advertisement is a way of communication with the customer of that brand. It helps to forms the basis of marketing. And if the advertisement part is strong and customer likes that then he/she will definitely like to buy that product. And if the advertisement part is weak and customers even don't want to see that advertisement then he/she will simple say that they don't like this product.

Quality is a great statement to make about your brand. It is better if your customers make that quality statement for you. Brand quality is the quality of the content and material which the brands offer. Quality also a very important factor in brand as people purchase branded products because of their quality so manufacturers have to maintain the quality of brand. If the quality decreases of any brand the customers of that product will also be decreased or switch to another branded product. Quality also effect the consciousness of the customer if the customer is like your brand and purchase it regularly then there should not be any difference in quality if difference occur customer will switch to another brand.

Rao (1989) as we know price and quality both are important for the brand image. The high quality in branded product shows that the companies are fulfilling the customers wants from that product. That's why there are willing to buy that branded product. So, if the perception of customer about quality is high then surly the price of that product will automatically high because they are offering quality products. If the quality of branded product is not high then may be customer thinks that they are not making better and goods product. That's why price and quality have positive correlation.

Grewal (1998) states that "brand name has been shown to be a critical cue for customer perceptions of product quality" in branding brand name show the quality of that product. Normally if we see or listen one well know branded product our first reaction will be yes that brand is very good we should buy that product. So, the product quality is also shown by brand name and the awareness of people about that brand. This shows that the people have knowledge about that product.

As brands carry significant symbolic values. Now a day's the person who is brand conscious he/she use the branded product as to express their selves. They want to show their inner self that we are wearing a branded product so we are able to stand in front of others. So, they are conscious and they wear branded products. This also shows their status and personality to other. They use branded product to express their personality.

Theoretical Framework

Price

Quality

Brand Consciousness

Brand Awareness

Methodology:

In my research, I adopted a quantitative approach, recognizing that this topic has been previously

explored by various scholars. My study was geographically focused on Lahore, a city where branded products are widely used in daily life. I visited several areas within Lahore including Gulberg, Liberty, and Fortress Stadium, as well as a university, to encompass a diverse range of individuals. This diversity included men, women, the young, the elderly, and the educated, all of whom were capable of responding to my inquiries.

The study's population consisted of consumers who frequently use branded products in Lahore. The goal was to understand their awareness of these products and to gauge the importance they place on factors like price and quality. For my sample, I selected individuals from this customer base using a simple random sampling method, ensuring every potential participant had an equal chance of being included.

The sample size for my study was 417 customers who use branded products. Despite the vast potential population, I had to limit the scope of my research. My analysis focused solely on these users, as they were more accessible for data collection.

The research tool was a structured questionnaire consisting of sixteen questions. These questions covered aspects such as quality, price, and brand awareness, along with other variables relevant to measuring brand consciousness. The questionnaire was designed to be straightforward, and participants were generally willing and able to provide responses.

Validity in research refers to the extent to which an indicator accurately measures the concept it is intended to measure. To address the issue of validity in my study, I employed face validity, which involved evaluating whether the questions in my survey were adequately designed to gather the necessary information. I discussed and refined these questions with my supervisor, and upon receiving approval, I proceeded to collect data from customers. Although gathering the complete dataset was challenging, I found that the respondents were cooperative, which facilitated the data collection process and made it more manageable.

For ensuring reliability, I utilized inter-item consistency reliability. This approach assesses the consistency of respondents' answers across all items in the survey, ensuring that each item independently measures the same concept. I compared the outcomes of one questionnaire with those of others to ascertain consistency and accuracy. This method was instrumental in obtaining reliable results for my study.

For collection of data I prepared a semi structured questionnaire which contained closed ended questions. I conducted self administrated survey in which I go to different places to fill the questionnaires by the customer of different branded products. I go to Gulberg, Liberty, Fortress Stadium and two universities which belong all categories of people i.e. male and females, young and old, well educated and low educated and people. In Pakistan we have many people who use branded products and in these areas I found people who were ready to response me. And help me to fill the data properly. The respondents were very cooperative and good in behaviour. So, for this reason it became easy for me to get data from various types of people and from various places SPSS used to analyze the data in addition to other suitable statistical techniques. This approach is chosen for two reasons. That it is good way to analyze qantitative data in real research now a day. And it helps researcher to equip its useful transferable skills. In SPSS I have done the Correlation

test, cross tabulation test, one way ANOVAs test, for analyzing the data.

DATA ANALYSIS

Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	15-20	49	11.8	11.8	11.8
	20-25	194	46.5	46.5	58.3
	25-30	99	23.7	23.7	82.0
	Above 30	75	18.0	18.0	100.0
	Total	417	100.0	100.0	

Age

This graph shows that there were 417 people who are in different age groups. Here 49 people are in between 15-20 year, 194 are in between 20-25 year, 99 are in 25-30 years, and 75 are above 30 years. It means this study have covered all age group's perceptions about branded product.

Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	140	33.6	33.6	33.6

Female	277	66.4	66.4	100.0
Total	417	100.0	100.0	

Gender

Gender

This graph shows that in total 417 respondents were there from which 140 males and 277 females. Those who were ready to give response about branded products

DESCRIPTIVE:

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
AVGQ	416	2.67	2.33	5.00	4.3045	.53696
AVGP	417	3.75	1.25	5.00	3.3897	.71354
AVGBA	417	1.33	1.00	2.33	1.5108	.36973
AVGBC	415	2.33	1.50	3.83	2.6996	.51908
Valid (listwise)	N 414					

This table shows the range mean and standard deviation of all the variables.

Correlations

	Quality	Price	Brand Awareness	Brand Consciousness
Pearson Correlation	1	.098*	-.046	.082
AVGQ Sig. (2-tailed)		.046	.351	.094
N	416	416	416	414
Pearson Correlation	.098*	1	-.043	.303**
AVGP Sig. (2-tailed)	.046		.378	.000
N	416	417	417	415
Pearson Correlation	-.046	-.043	1	-.136**
AVGBA Sig. (2-tailed)	.351	.378		.005
N	416	417	417	415
Pearson Correlation	.082	.303**	-.136**	1
AVGBC Sig. (2-tailed)	.094	.000	.005	
N	414	415	415	415

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above table reveals the relation of brand consciousness with quality, price and brand awareness. Brand consciousness is correlated with price and the relation is significant even at a level of 0.05. The correlation coefficient is .098 for the price.

Conclusion:

This research conducted to check that how many people are really conscious about branded products. The results of my findings given me a lot of experience, I had interact with a lot of people who were in different age group. As results show that there were 417 respondents from which 33.6% are male and 66.4% are female. 60.4% people are conscious about branded products. And from which 39.3 respondents consider that they are not loyal with their brands and 34.3% consider they are and 26.4% they are very loyal with their brands. If we look gender wise male and female are more conscious about brands but between male and female of age group if 20-25 females are more brand conscious. These days, people focus on brand name and overall results show people are aware of the brands. Dodds (1991, 316) also concluded that both quality and brand name had a positive effect on willingness to buy.

And the results shows that new generation are more moving towards branded products instead of old people. However in Pakistan many brands are targeting new generation with different segments. This study will help brands to target which segment and make them aware for their brands.

Discussion:

This study reveals a notable variation in brand consciousness among individuals, primarily influenced by gender differences. This phenomenon can be linked to the increasing trends in globalization, where trade liberalization has enabled brands to operate on an international scale. Consequently, the availability of brands has expanded globally, complemented by enhanced

marketing and promotional strategies that amplify consumer perceptions of brand equity and associations. A significant disparity in brand consciousness between genders was observed, with females exhibiting higher levels of brand consciousness than males. This finding aligns with previous research indicating that females tend to engage more in shopping and information-seeking before making purchases (Punj & Staelin, 1983; Cobb & Hoyer, 1985). This suggests that females invest considerable effort in researching product brands.

The research further underscores that females are significantly more brand conscious than males, largely due to their heightened concern for social image. They often use brands as a means to establish their identity and status within society. Brand associations, therefore, play a crucial role in their purchasing decisions.

Previous studies in the United States have indicated varying levels of brand consciousness based on age. Marx (1995) noted that college students are particularly brand conscious. Liebeck (1996) found that high school students exhibit a high degree of brand consciousness, a concern for their parents. However, this study found that individuals aged 20-25 are significantly more brand conscious than those aged 25-30 or above 30. This could be due to marketers targeting younger generations to secure lifelong customers or because this age group possesses considerable purchasing power.

The insights from this study are invaluable for both domestic and global companies in shaping their product and marketing strategies according to consumer preferences and motivations. Additionally, the findings provide essential knowledge for educators addressing consumerism and youth brand consciousness. This research can also lay the groundwork for future studies in various international markets.

Limitations & Future Studies:

This study is subject to a few limitations which constrain the breadth and applicability of its conclusions. Firstly, the data was derived from a convenience sample, limiting its representativeness and the extent to which findings can be generalized to a broader geographic area. Secondly, the influence of national brands on respondents' perceptions cannot be overlooked. Brands like Nike and Levi's, known for quality, or those perceived as "cool," inevitably impact the results. Additionally, the variables used in analyzing purchasing decisions – such as price, brand, previous experience, and quality – could benefit from more precise definitions. The close similarity in responses across some clothing categories suggests the possibility of variable contamination, which could be minimized through clearer definition of these variables.

Recommendations for Future Research:

1. Inclusion of Older Age Groups: Future studies should include older demographics to assess how globalization impacts different generations in terms of brand consciousness.
2. Focus on Self-Image and Gender Differences: Additional research into self-image and gender-specific consumer behavior, particularly examining why women may be more brand conscious, could provide deeper insights.

3. Exploration of National Brand Influence: Investigating whether consumer decisions are driven by specific characteristics associated with national brands or by the status of the brand itself could offer valuable information.

4. Larger Sample Size: A more extensive sample could enhance the validity of the study's findings and offer a clearer picture of consumer behavior.

5. Examination of Young Consumers: Given the unique media-saturated, brand-conscious upbringing of the younger generation, as highlighted in a Business Week article (Neuborne, 1999), further research is needed to understand their distinct response patterns to advertising and brand loyalty.

6. Consideration of Economic Factors: A survey that takes into account economic variables, such as regular income and financial constraints, would provide a more nuanced understanding of consumer behavior. People with higher incomes may exhibit different patterns, possibly prioritizing brand loyalty over brand awareness.

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